

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH STORYTELLING FOR A1 –B2 LEARNERS

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Abstract. *Storytelling and narration are powerful tools that engage our imagination, creativity, and language skills . Considering the nature of human beings as storytellers, teachers can use storytelling as a teaching method in English classrooms. The aim with this study is to discuss the storytelling teaching method adopted in ELT Classroom . This study tries to answer the research question: to what extent story telling is effective in developing and the speaking skill in English of the low students? The stories, which represent the proposed program, were used to measure the four sub-skills; predicting, telling the main idea, recognizing characters and summarizing the events. This study has also suggested that further researches should be conducted on the effect of storytelling technique of learning English skills. This task oriented language learning tool enhances the imaginary capability of the students and provides better contexts of learning English language. This is the method in which students are given themes to form stories which serves as a technique to develop multi-skills like power of imagination, confidence, fluency, problem solving attitude, team work, empathy etc.*

Keywords: *storytelling, emotional intelligence, vocabulary, structure, motivation, acquisition*

Аннотация. *Рассказывание историй и повествование — это мощные инструменты, которые задействуют наше воображение, творческие способности и языковые навыки. Учитывая природу людей как рассказчиков, учителя могут использовать рассказывание историй в качестве метода обучения на уроках английского языка. Целью данного исследования является обсуждение метода обучения рассказыванию историй, принятого в классе ELT. Это исследование пытается ответить на исследовательский вопрос: в какой степени рассказывание историй эффективно для развития навыков разговорной речи на английском языке у учащихся с низким уровнем знаний? Истории, представляющие предлагаемую программу, использовались для измерения четырех поднавыков; прогнозирование, изложение основной мысли, узнавание персонажей и обобщение событий. Это исследование также показало, что следует провести дальнейшие исследования влияния техники рассказывания историй на изучение навыков английского языка. Этот ориентированный на задачи инструмент изучения языка расширяет воображаемые возможности учащихся и обеспечивает лучшие условия для изучения английского языка. Это метод, при котором учащимся даются темы для формирования историй, который служит методом развития нескольких навыков, таких как сила воображения, уверенность, беглость речи, подход к решению проблем, работа в команде, сочувствие и т. д.*

Introduction. “Tell me a fact and I’ll learn. Tell me the truth and I’ll believe. But tell me a story and it will live in my heart forever”. - An Indian Proverb.

Storytelling, the art of narrating a tale from memory rather than reading is one of the oldest of all art forms. Storytelling is the original form of teaching and has the potential of fostering emotional intelligence and helps the child gain insight into human behavior. It also promotes language learning by enriching learners' vocabulary and acquiring new language structures. Moreover, storytelling can provide a motivating and low anxiety context for language learning. The storytelling tips given in this article are meant to help the teacher-as-storyteller as s/he prepares for a storytelling "performance" for students.

Because language is an interactive process, children learning a language need ample opportunity to interact in a meaningful, interesting context and play with the language while developing vocabulary and structures. They need the collaboration of their peers and teachers in creating meaningful contexts and negotiating meanings in those context.

The concept of learning is often considered to be different from acquisition. Acquisition is a natural process. A child would begin the process of first language acquisition at very early age. He would get enough exposure from his living environment by listening consciously or unconsciously to what people say around him. Learning process is different from acquisition. Students are placed in classroom settings, following teachers' instructions.

The teacher should consider about many aspects that would affect the process of students' learning a second language for example, teaching environment, teaching method and materials, students' mentality, their ages and gender and so on.

The aim in the speaking skill is challenging, so it is not easy thing. The teachers and students may face some problems in the teaching and learning of speaking. The inconvenient condition was appeared by the monotonous teaching technique used by some teachers. Also sometimes the classroom activities tended to be teacher centered. Some students sometimes were only passive in the teaching and learning process. This is the challenge for the teachers to control the students' success in learning, they should be more creative.

More subject knowledge is not enough to get employed. Good communication skill in general and in English language in particular has an upper hand to succeed in this competitive world.

Defined storytelling as a knowledge management technique, a way of distributing information , targeted to audiences and a sense of information, she added

that stories provide natural connection between events and concepts and finally , she added that visual storytelling is a way of telling stories through images

Certain Characteristics of Storytelling

- 1 It provokes curiosity.
 - 2 It evokes student's imagination and interest in language skill.
 - 3 It builds vocabulary, comprehension, story sequencing.
 - 4 It improves listening and oral communication skills.
 - 3 It is an interactive and co-operative process.
 - 4 As an art it is an enjoyable tool for practicing language learning skills and verbal expressions.
 - 5 It binds listeners together.
 - 6 It helps the listener to remember.
 - 7 It uses all kinds of language conventions to make the story vivid.
 - 8 It makes listeners forget their misery.
- To enable the students to learn English language skills
 - To enhance their confidence and speaking skill
 - To increase the student's knowledge of vocabulary, structure, context and grammar
 - To develop problem solving skills
 - To shed inhibition
 - To teach narrative structure and practice description
 - To create interest and develop listening comprehension
 - To improve pronunciation and intonation
 - To enhance the skills of connecting to content, connecting to learners and modeling
 - To create fluency in speaking and to think about narration in writing
 - To encourage interaction and share culture

Storytelling and narration can be an excellent way to improve your language skills while also enhancing your cultural knowledge and creativity. In this article, we'll explore the benefits of practicing a language through storytelling and narration, as well as some tips and techniques to make the most out of this language method method.

It can be defined as the transmission of events in words, images and sounds in the shape of narrative genre which should include plot, characters and events. It is sometimes called narrative knowledge that attempts to relate events in the form of a story. Moreover, it is the act of bestowing life to stories through the inflection in one's voice rhythm, facial expression and hand movement. Before the teacher starts the activity, he should

* Mention that communication involves some factors, like sender, receiver, feedback, purpose, etc. It also involves appropriate use of language to make it effective.

* Show the students some videos on effective and ineffective communication. Point out and explain the barriers.

* Gives them a list of formulaic expressions/Speech Acts to be used for different language functions and asks the learners to implement those through storytelling.

For the Treatment

• The teacher prepares the outlines of stories and writes them separately on colored papers and hangs them

with the help of a thread on the white board.

• The students are formed into groups of 5 members.

• Each group is asked to pick up a paper from the white board.

• Groups are then given 15 minutes time to develop a story from the given outline.

• They are then asked to come along with their group members and narrate the story before the class.

• The best group is awarded.

Assignment

a) Tell a story and make us laugh

I was in the cinema and I was watching a film and half way through the person next to me the mobile phone rang and answered it and began to have conversation.....

(Complete the story)

b) Tell a story and keep the mystery till the end.

The other morning I heard a knock at the door. I was expecting a package so I jumped out of the shower,

dripping wet, and threw on my bath robe.....

(Complete the story)

c) Tell us a story and take us to a fairly-land

Many moons ago in my backyard a good looking girl named Babli was walking along minding her own

business. Suddenly she saw.....

The Queen was so happy that she jumped with joy.

(Complete the story)

d) Tell us horror story

People are given a miracle drug that ensures that their children are born with the ability to become extremely intelligent. But the drug backfires and the children are born deformed. Scientific labs steal the children to cover up their mistakes and hide them trying to learn where they went wrong....

(Complete the story)

e) Tell us a romantic story and make us cry

Boy meets girl.

Girl meets boy.

Boy and girl fell in love. Something keeps the boy and the girl from being together.

Conflict is solved. Sad ending..... (Complete the story)

f) Tell us a story with a moral at the end

Not everyone who drops shit on you is your enemy.

Not everyone who gets you out of shit is your friend.

When you are in deep shit, keep your mouth shut.

(Complete the story)

There are many other types of methods for activities which contribute a big part for developing speaking skills among the A1-B2 learners:

- Find suitable title for some parts of the story
- Change the following words to the antonyms
- Change the following words to the synonyms
- Describe the main characters of the story
- How would you end this miserable story with a happier favorably ending?
- Describe positive and negative moments of the story
- Watching movies , cartoons
- Answering the questions

- Fill the gaps
- Make up oral questions

The Benefits of Storytelling and Narration for Language Learning

Storytelling and narration are powerful tools that engage our imagination, creativity, and language skills. When you practice a language through storytelling and narration, you'll enjoy several benefits, including:

- **Improving Your Speaking Skills**

Recounting a story or narrating an event requires you to put your language skills to use. You'll have to structure your sentences, use appropriate vocabulary, and convey your message clearly and effectively. As you practice speaking through storytelling and narration, you'll naturally improve your speaking skills, become more fluent, and gain confidence in your ability to communicate in your target language.

- **Enhancing Your Listening Skills**

Listening to stories and narratives can be just as beneficial as telling them. By listening to native speakers, you'll improve your ability to understand natural speech patterns, intonation, and pronunciation. You'll also learn new words and expressions in context, which can help you expand your vocabulary and improve your comprehension skills.

- **Developing Cultural Knowledge**

Storytelling and narration are an essential part of many cultures, and by engaging in this practice, you'll gain a deeper understanding of the cultural context of the language you're learning. You'll learn about the values, beliefs, and traditions of the people who speak the language, which can enhance your overall language learning experience.

- **Boosting Your Creativity**

Telling stories requires creativity and imagination, and by practicing storytelling and narration, you'll develop these skills. You'll learn how to structure a story, create engaging characters, and use descriptive language to convey your message effectively. These skills can be transferable to other areas of your life, such as writing and public speaking

- Demonstrating a clear understanding of the rhetorical situation, including purpose, context, audience and genre.

- Students will be able to exchange information and ideas clearly and effectively.
- Will be able to contribute in a brain storming exercise.
- Develop active listening skill.
- Students will be able to gather confidence in speaking in the target language.
- Will be able to use appropriate expressions for specific situation and audience.
- It will reduce students' inhibitions.
- Students will able to present their ideas and information in a clear structured way.
- Will be able to speak effectively in public.
- Building confidence.
- Engage independently in the highest levels of creative thinking.
- Students will speak to explore, extend, clarify, and reflect on their thoughts, ideas, feelings, and experiences.

Evaluation

- Communication Skills (speak clearly, use proper expressions)
- Confidence level
- Useful language and vocabulary
- Summarizing techniques
- Useful expression
- Analysis of plot and character
- Language Diction
- Checking non-verbal aspects
- Interpersonal skill
- Body Language
- Team Work
- Audience Control

Conclusion

The goal of this paper was to provide a brief introduction to the current research activity in the areas of storytelling and learning English language. Story telling technique is believed to be one of the entertaining techniques that can be used with learners in order to develop their English language skill. Actually, storytelling technique attracts student's attention and higher concentration, this technique provokes prediction and expectation of events. Consequently, those effects lead to

deeper comprehension, enjoyment and happiness. Moreover, storytelling technique has great effects on students in their learning of English language. It changes the class room environment from a dry boring one to a warm environment full of student's concentration, participation and production.

References:

1. **Brown, H.D.** 2001 Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. New York: Addison Wesley Longmn Inc.
2. **Brown, H.D.** (1994). Principles of Language Learning and Teaching. (3 ed).
3. **Burns, A. & Joyce, H.** 1999 Focus on Speaking. National Centre for English Language Teaching and Reserch. Sydney Macquarie.
4. **Celce, M & Murcia.** 2001 Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language. (3rd ed). Boston: Heinle & Heinle.
5. **Creswell, J.W.**2003. Research Design, Second Edition. California: SagePublications, Inc.
6. **Farhady.** 1982 Research Design and Statistic for Applied Linguistics. Massachusetts: Newburry House Publisher, Inc.
7. **Harmer, J.** 2004. How to Teach English : An introduction to the practice of English Language Teaching. Kualalumpur: Longman **New York:** Cambridge University
8. Press. Richards, J. C. & Renandya, W. A. (Eds.) (2002). Methodology in Language Teaching an Anthology of Current Practice.
9. **Cambridge:** Cambridge University Press.Scott, P. (1985). Storytelling: A guide to the art.
10. New South Wales: Primary English Teaching Association. Stone, R. J. (1996).